

46/102428 (see table). None, however, exceeded the check Shanyou 10 (Zhenshan 97 A/Milyang 46). The hulling (brown rice) rate of most of the hybrids was higher than that of their parents and of the check combination, averaging 8.14%.

Grain length was between that of their corresponding parents, and usually more

similar to that of the longer grained parent. All hybrids showed some chalkiness, but were far less chalky than 02428.

Amylose content (AC) was 16.9-28.3%. AC of Minghui 63/102428 and IRI371/02428 exceeded that of their high parent whereas that of IRI361/02428 and Milyang 46/02428 was below that of

their low parents. None of the six hybrids displayed an obvious gel consistency pattern. Alkali digestion values averaged around 4.

The results indicate that the grain quality of the six intersubspecies hybrids was superior to that of the leading intrasubspecies combination Shanyou 10. □

Phenological and quality aspects of grains of rice *O. sativa* L.

A. A. Vidal and M. D. Asborn, Estacion Experimental Ing. Agr. Julio Hirschhorn, Facultad de Ciencias Agrarias y Forestales, Universidad Nacional de la Plata, Buenos Aires, Argentina

Environmental conditions influence the phenological and quality characteristics of rice grain. Lower ambient temperatures during rice growth shorten the germination and vegetative phase.

Lower temperatures during grain development tend to produce higher amylose content (AC) levels and lower values for gelatinization temperature (GT) of starch than at average temperatures.

Alkali spreading value and amylose content of commercial grain types under 2 ambient temperatures.^a

Grain type	Varieties (no.)	Alkali spreading value ^b (GT index)		Amylose content ^b (% db)	
		Temp A (21.9 °C)	Temp B (18.6 °C)	Temp A (21.9 °C)	Temp B (18.6 °C)
Medium	3	5.63 a	5.71 b	12.5 a	17.4 b
Long-wide	3	5.28 a	5.76 b	18.1 a	19.5 b
Short	2	6.42 a	6.51 b	16.2 a	17.5 b
Long-slender	17	5.20 a	5.62 b	22.7 a	23.1 b
GT LSD (0.05) = 0.13		AC LSD (0.05) = 0.91			
CV (%) = 3.06		CV (%) = 6.87			

^aA = normal temperature condition (21.9 °C), B = 30 d after October (18.6 °C). In the row, values with the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

We studied the effect of ambient temperature on 25 rice varieties for 3 yr under two temperature conditions.

The experiment was laid out in a random block design with four replications in factorial 2 × 4 × 4. Alkali spreading value ranged from 2.5 in Century Patna 231 to 7 in IRGA409

(see table). AC ranged from 14% in Norin 20 to 27% in IRGA409. We divided the varieties into four sample groups based on their commercial grain types: medium, long-wide, short, long-slender. Under the two temperatures, the groups differed significantly in AC and GT (see table). □

Pest resistance—diseases

Reexamination of linkage relationships between blast (BI) resistance genes *Pi-i* and *Pi-z* using near-isogenic lines (NILs) of rice

K. Ise, National Agricultural Research Center (NARC), Tsukuba, Ibaraki, Japan

Pi-i and *Pi-z* are in the sixth linkage group on current linkage maps. *Pi-z* was reported to have linkage relations to marker genes *C*, *alk*, and *Lm (Se-1)*, all belonging to the sixth linkage group. The *Pi-i* locus was reported to be linked to the *Pi-z* locus, with a recombination value of about 30% in the repulsion phase. I found the loci independent of the other, based on F₂ segregation data using NILs, except for the BI resistance genes.

We have been developing NILs by repeatedly backcrossing the Japanese cultivar Nipponbare to different sources of resistance to the B1 fungus *Pyricularia oryzae* Cavara. The recurrent parent is a japonica cultivar susceptible to most of the B1 isolates collected in Japan. The NILs are similar to Nipponbare in height, maturity, and appearance. The pedigrees and resistance genes of NILs used in this

research are in Table 1. *Pi-z'* is a multiple allele of the *Pi-z* locus, which was introduced to a japonica line from an indica variety.

Seedlings of parental lines and F₂ plants were grown in a greenhouse. They were inoculated at the four- to five-leaf stage by spraying with an aqueous spore suspension of about 3 × 10⁵ conidia/ml. Isolates IBOS 1-1-1 and Ken 54-20 were used as the inoculum. They belong to the most common race in Japan, race 3.

Table 1. Pedigrees of NILs with BI resistance.

Line	Resistance gene	Pedigree ^a	Source of resistance	
			Cultivar	Origin
Kanto-IL 5	<i>Pi-z</i>	Nipponbare *3//Ou 287/2* Nipponbare	Zenith	USA
Kanto-IL 7	<i>Pi-i</i>	Nipponbare *3//Todorokiwase/2* Nipponbare	Todorokiwase	Japan
Kanto-IL 8	<i>Pi-z'</i>	Nipponbare *3//73-B205/2* Nipponbare	Morak Sepilai	Malaysia

^aOu 287 = Fukunishiki/Kiyonishiki Fukunishiki: 597/Zenith/597/3/Hatsunishiki. 73-B205 = Morak Sepilai/5 * Fujisaka 5.

Table 2. Segregation for reaction to 2 isolates (race 003) of *Pyricularia oryzae* in the F₂ populations between NILS.^a

Cultivar, line, or cross	Seedlings (no.)			Goodness of fit		
	Resistant	Susceptible	Total	$\chi^2(3:1)$	$\chi^2(15:1)$	Probability
Isolate IBOS 1-1-1						
Nipponbare (\pm)	0	9	9			
Kanto-IL 7 (<i>Pi-i</i>)	10	0	10			
NipponbareKanto-IL 7	146	53	199	0.2831		0.50 - 0.60
Nipponbare (\pm)	0	8	8			
Kanto-IL 8 (<i>Pi-z'</i>)	9	0	9			
NipponbareKanto-IL 8	148	42	190	0.8491		0.30 - 0.40
Nipponbare (\pm)	0	10	10			
Kanto-IL 5 (<i>Pi-z</i>)	10	0	10			
NipponbareKanto-IL 5	143	51	194	0.1718		0.60 - 0.70
Isolate IBOS 1-1-1						
Nipponbare (\pm)	0	39	39			
Kanto-IL 7 (<i>Pi-i</i>)	10	0	10			
Kato-IL 8 (<i>Pi-z'</i>)	9	0	9			
Kanto-IL 7/Kanto-IL 8	350	26	376	0.2837		0.50 - 0.60
Nipponbare (\pm)	0	41	41			
Kanto-IL 5 (<i>Pi-z</i>)	10	0	10			
Kanto-IL 7 (<i>Pi-i</i>)	10	0	10			
Kanto-IL 5/Kanto-IL 7	462	35	497	0.5324		0.40 - 0.50
Isolate Ken 54-20						
Nipponbare (\pm)	0	10	10			
Kanto-IL 7 (<i>Pi-i</i>)	10	0	10			
Kanto-IL 8 (<i>Pi-z'</i>)	10	0	10			
Kanto-IL 7/Kanto-IL 8	184	13	197	0.0409		0.80 - 0.90
Nipponbare (\pm)	0	10	10			
Kanto-IL 5 (<i>Pi-z</i>)	10	0	10			
Kanto-IL 7 (<i>Pi-i</i>)	10	0	10			
Kanto-IL 5/Kanto-IL 7	191	13	204	0.0052		0.90 - 0.95

^a Blast resistance gene for each line is in parentheses.

Disease reactions were scored about 7 d after inoculation.

Inoculated seedlings clearly segregated into resistant and susceptible classes. Each segregation of F₂ populations derived from crosses between three NILs and the recurrent parent gave a good fit to a 3 resistant: 1 susceptible ratio. This shows that each NIL has a single dominant gene for resistance to the isolate IBOS 1-1-1 (Table 2).

Each segregation of four F₂ populations derived from crosses between the NIL with *Pi-i* and the NILs with *Pi-z* or *Pi-z'* gave a good fit to a 15 resistant: 1 susceptible ratio. This indicates that two independent dominant genes conferred resistance to the isolates belonging to race 3 (Table 2). These segregation patterns indicate no linkage relationships between *Pi-i* and *Pi-z* loci.

Some workers previously used breeding lines with *Pi-z* derived from distantly related crosses and a Japanese cultivar with *Pi-i* genetic analyses. These different genetic backgrounds or modifier gene(s) may cause an excess of resistant segregants in the F₂ populations, suggesting linkage in the repulsion phase. The NILs provide excellent material for characterizing each gene and for further genetic and pathologic studies. □

Pest resistance—insects

Identification of a new Asian rice gall midge (GM) population in Bhandara District, Maharashtra, India, and highly resistant genotypes

P. S. P. Rao, Central Rice Research Institute (CRRRI), Cuttack, Orissa; and H. G. Kandalakar, National Agricultural Research Program (NARP) Substation, Sakoli, Bhandara District, Maharashtra, India

Four biotypes (I to IV) of the Asian rice GM *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae) from different rice areas of India have been identified and characterized. Earlier trials with limited differentials showed that the Sakoli GM was similar to that from north

coastal Andhra Pradesh (NCAP) (biotype IV). Many GM-resistant rice donors and cultures, however, were susceptible at Sakoli, an area where GM is endemic. We studied 36 donors and cultures with known reactions to the biotypes during 1990 and 1991 kharif (monsoons).

Reaction of differentials to Indian GM biotypes from different locations, 1990-91 kharif. ^a

Biotype	Location	Reaction of differentials									
		Eswara-korra	Orumun-dakan	CR308-408	CR309-268	PTB10	R296-120	CR157-212	Vellu-tha-cheera	CRS7-Kaka-MR 1523	Kakatiya
I	Warangal, Andhra Pradesh (AP)	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
II	Cuttack, Orissa	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S
III	Ranchi, Bihar	R	-	-	R	R	R	R	R	S	R
IV	Srikakulam, North Coastal AP	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R
V	Sakoli, Maharashtra	R	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	S

^aS = susceptible, R = resistant.

The seed originated from CRRRI's insect-resistant donor garden. It was selected over several years for GM resistance under high GM pressure in the field.

The entries were transplanted in early August in Cuttack and in late August in Sakoli to allow for peak GM infestation by the 50-60 d after planting. We adopted